

Is AI A New Frontier in Healthcare?

A DISCUSSION OF THE APPLICATIONS AND ETHICAL
IMPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE
HEALTHCARE SECTOR

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Abstract

This paper examines the ethical implications of implementing artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare, focusing on fairness, transparency, and autonomy issues. It discusses potential challenges and offers solutions to mitigate biases, enhance transparency, assign accountability, and uphold patient autonomy. Fairness is explored through algorithmic biases and the need for inclusive and equitable healthcare AI systems. Transparency is addressed by considering the transparency fallacy and proposing selective information sharing through trusted intermediaries. Accountability and liability are discussed, emphasising the shared responsibility between AI software vendors and healthcare professionals. The role of patients and informed consent is examined, highlighting the importance of patient autonomy, risk mitigation, and patient engagement in the AI adoption process. While acknowledging the ethical challenges, the paper encourages continued dialogue to leverage the potential benefits of AI in healthcare. Future work is suggested to explore alternative ethical frameworks and address unresolved questions, such as collective responsibility and the development of morally responsible AI agents.

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1 *Introduction*

Artificial intelligence (AI) is defined as “the ability of computers to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence” (Webster 6). As AI technology becomes more mature and less costly, it has gained popularity in the field of healthcare research, education, and practice; many researchers believe it will cause the next major revolution in the healthcare sector (Challen et al. 231; Duggal et al. 1; Eshwar 1). It has also been proven that AI can deliver personalised services and recommendations, triage clinical cases, provide remote care, improve patient outcomes, increase the accuracy and efficiency of diagnosis and treatment processes, lowering long-term costs, and assist in administrative tasks (Chan and Petrikat 58; Davenport and Kalakota 96; Wen and Huang 217).

However, as AI begins to be adopted in the field, there have been voices of concern regarding potential implications, especially on a few fundamental ethical values, that it may bring. Would AI perpetuate social biases and prejudices in its judgements? How does AI affect access to healthcare for different communities? What does it mean for medical AI to be “transparent”? Who should be accountable for the AI’s behaviour? To what extent would AI diminish patient participation? Can AI help improve overall well-being in society? This work will discuss these questions in depth and, when applicable, also suggest some potential measures that ensure a smoother integration of AI systems in healthcare agencies.

2 Fairness, inclusivity, and equity

Before this section begins, the distinction between “equity” and “equality” must be outlined. While equality simply means “sameness in treatment by asserting the fundamental or natural equality of all persons”, equity is “associated with fairness or justice in the provision of [...] benefits” and “takes individual circumstances into consideration” (Espinoza 345). This section will concentrate on reaching “equity” or, in other words, using healthcare AI in a way that reduces social discrimination by allocating resources to where they are needed.

Increased adoption of intelligent algorithms related to healthcare has accumulated real-life cases for AI designers to study. Unfortunately, many involve misjudgements due to discrimination against protected social groups (Thomasian et al. 602–03). Several patterns emerge from these incidents: racial/ethnic bias, gender bias, and socioeconomic bias, among others. Most, if not all, reflect preferences from practitioners in the current healthcare system (Gianfrancesco et al. 1546; Nori et al. 20; Parikh and Helmchen 4; Thomasian et al. 602–03). Moreover, these biases are often superimposed, as, through a lens of intersectionality, many individuals are discriminated against due to multiple identity markers. Eliminating discrimination in healthcare AI is especially meaningful because, as Wu and Liu indicated, a lack of inclusivity and equity in the system can affect all users’ safety and well-being (6). Neglecting this aspect could jeopardise equitable access to healthcare and lead to divergence in treatment, exacerbating social inequality amongst different groups (Aquino et al. 1).

2.1 Biases and inequities in healthcare AI

Biases may surface in different stages of an AI model: conception, development and implementation (Leslie et al. 1). In the conception stage, the model's input parameters may be designed in a manner that lacks inclusivity. There may be overlooked yet clinically relevant demographic variables that will place members of certain communities at a disadvantage (Leslie et al. 1). As an example, specific dermatological illnesses related to pigmented lesions are closely associated with skin colour; because of this, it may be reasoned that ethnicity could play a major role in accurately identifying such symptoms (Adamson and Smith 1247–48). However, this principle is an extremely thin line to tread. Researchers such as Vyas et al. listed various examples to prove how identifying as different races, especially Black, could lead to unreliable results produced by various clinical tools (874–78). Consequently, the extent to which race, or any other sensitive personal label for that matter, is relevant must be discussed thoroughly by experts in the field before it can be applied to a model.

Other than the input, bias may also occur when selecting the output of the model as a proxy to assess clinical situations (Dortche et al. 2). Obermeyer et al. published a well-cited study on the propagation of racism in AI due to the ineffective proxy choice of healthcare costs (447); comparably, Kakani et al. investigated the unfair distribution of relief funding based on revenue (1002). One explanation for this failure is that the models neglect to consider historically unequal access to healthcare resources: in the case proposed by Obermeyer et al., the algorithm may be operating under the assumption that illnesses manifest similarly in both dominant and minority groups, while the latter may have more severe symptoms due to their

tendency to be underdiagnosed and mistreated by physicians. This explanation seems to be supported by the data in the publication, which shows how resolving this discrepancy delivers an additional 17.7% to 46.5% support for Black patients (448–49).

In the development stage, discrimination stems chiefly from the training dataset. There are generally three types of flaws with a biased dataset: missing data, underestimation, and misclassification (Gianfrancesco et al. 1544). Missing data refers to the algorithm's inability to correctly interpret non-uniform training data. According to Gianfrancesco et al., it would be more challenging to identify certain illnesses for patients who cannot afford to visit healthcare institutions as often or visit multiple healthcare institutions because the evidence to base the diagnosis on would be limited (1545). This may not be an uncommon issue: two-thirds of commercial insurance plans, which are closely related to healthcare data, report neither fully nor partially complete racial information (Ng et al. 549).

Underestimation refers to the problems caused by the relatively small sample size of minority groups represented in the dataset; misclassification describes the situation when the patient is over- or under-diagnosed, usually due to the implicit biases of the practitioner (Gianfrancesco et al. 1546). These issues are inter-related and have been encountered by multiple sub-disciplines (Dortche et al. 2). In radiology, Seyyed-Kalantari et al. found out that chest radiograph classifiers “consistently and selectively underdiagnosed under-served patient populations”, especially “intersectional under-served subpopulations” (2176). In dermatology, Adamson and Smith reported that “most ML programs are largely learning on light skin”, and that, given that the biggest public dataset available mostly contains light-skinned individuals, all

algorithms may “underperform” when it comes to patients of colour (1247). In cardiology, Tahhan et al. discovered that “older patients and women remain significantly underrepresented in [acute coronary syndrome] trials” (718). Correspondingly, Tat et al. identified that “[women] and minority groups are historically under-represented”, female and Black patients are consistently under-reported, “men are 2–5 times more likely to be referred to a cardiologist for management than women”, and “Black patients in the emergency room are 40% less likely to receive pain medication than White patients” (e635). These results all point to one conclusion: if AI continues to be trained on historical data without proper amendments, it will undeniably revive the detrimental discrimination seen in the past and, to a great extent, in the present too. As researchers at Microsoft and OpenAI observed with GPT-4, before biases can be recognised and mitigated properly, extensive reliance on AI will only propagate these long-term disparities, resulting in sustained inadequate care (Nori et al. 20).

In the implementation stage, Gianfrancesco et al. pointed out a critical aspect regarding generalised models, arguing that models trained at one institution will not necessarily apply to another (1545). This is because different facilities may serve different types of patients, depending on the type of care provided. As a result, some institutions may have proportionally larger patient data of a certain race, gender, socioeconomic status and, for specialised centres, even a certain disease. This may not constitute a hindrance in the context of that specific institution, but if this system is to be used externally, the model must be trained on a larger, more diverse dataset.

Another form of discrimination in the implementation stage, unrelated to the actual model, is the unfair distribution of technology. There seems to be a direct correlation between the adoption of AI and the economic conditions in different countries, as AI is “resource-intensive” and requires “large amounts of data, skills, and computing power for development and deployment” (Brady and Neri 5; Vuong et al. 3). This poses a serious issue for developing countries that cannot afford the research and development of medical AI. This deficiency in cutting-edge technology may put them in a more disadvantageous and vulnerable position compared to developed countries that own the technology, even causing political tensions.

2.2 Achieving fairness and equity

Fairness and equity are principles at the core of most AI regulation frameworks, including the “Quintuple Aim” (Patient Experience, Equity & Inclusion, Reducing Cost, Population Health and Care Team Well-being) and the WHO guidelines (Itchhaporia 2263; Matheny et al. 2; Reis et al. 23–30). However, compared to other principles, such as the promotion of well-being and safety, equity seems to be marginally less discussed in the literature (Wu and Liu 6). To reach this goal, biases reviewed in Section 2.1 must be eliminated. Some government agencies, such as the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in the United States, have already released guidance on regulations to address algorithmic biases in the healthcare AI systems (United States, Food and Drug Administration, Center for Devices and Radiological Health 5).

There are three main themes in AI justice: identification, quantification and eradication of biases (Thiebes et al. 454). The first one is quite intuitive: AI developers have the responsibility to familiarise themselves with common types of bias, identify them early in the development

process of their product, and minimise downstream impacts in later stages (Zhang and Zhang 11). Gerke et al. called this responsibility “ethics by design”, as opposed to considering ethical issues only after the product has been developed and tested (332–33). Regarding the quantification of biases and justice, utility software has been developed to aid researchers in measuring discovered biases, such as AI Fairness 360 (AIF360) by IBM. The main goal is to “promote a deeper understanding of fairness metrics and mitigation techniques” (Bellamy et al. 1). Likewise, PROBAST is another tool that can assess the risk of bias (ROB) in prediction models (Wolff et al. 51). Both tools help with understanding bias more quantitatively.

After identifying and understanding biases, actions must then be taken to diminish them as much as possible, if not eliminate them. Mehrabi et al. divided these actions into three categories: pre-processing, where the data is transformed before the model even has access; in-processing, where data is manipulated during the training of the model; and post-processing, where the correction occurs after the model (usually a black box in these scenarios) outputs some data (Mehrabi et al. 13–14). van de Sande et al. further separated the development process into multiple phases; the most interesting ones are elaborated on below (2–5).

The first step should be assessing existing work. Before a healthcare institution decides to develop a model, they should evaluate available models on the market, especially the ones that are officially approved (van de Sande et al. 3). These commercial solutions tend to be more robust and well-tested, and the institution may learn from them even if they don’t completely fulfil the requirements. A suitable framework for the evaluation of medical AI is the ECLAIR guidelines, which contain five properties: relevance, performance and validation, usability and

integration, regulatory and legal aspects, and financial and support services considerations (Omoumi et al. 3788–89). There are also alternative reporting guidelines focusing on different qualities, such as SPIRIT-AI (Rivera et al. e552–55), CONSORT-AI (Liu et al. 1367–70) and TRIPOD (Collins et al. 6–7).

The second step is to de-bias the dataset used to train the model. Much effort has been dedicated to reducing imbalanced data, with recommendations for both the producers and the consumers of datasets. For the producers, it is their responsibility to provide supporting datasheets detailing the motivation, composition, collection and limitation of the data so that developers using them will be alert for potential biases that may occur (Geburu et al. 86). Besides, they are encouraged to openly share their data (after desensitising any records that may cause privacy concerns) so that developers can have a diverse range of datasets to choose from, reducing the likelihood of biases (Norori et al. 5–6). For the consumers, some statistical techniques recommended are massaging the dataset, preferential sampling, and disparate impact removal (Mehrabi et al. 14). During training, approaches such as oversampling minority groups, reporting uncertainty for high-risk groups, and assigning less weight to follow-up records to address the problem of missing data can be taken (Parikh et al. 2378). Both producers and consumers are advised to consciously collect additional data from minority groups and manually augment the dataset. Norori et al. suggested that in some cases, creative AI models like Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) can even be used to generate synthetic data for underrepresented classes (6).

The third step is to train and validate the performance of the model. The first type, internal validation, is a standard training process that usually incorporates a train-validation split on the source dataset. Most data go into training the model, and the rest is reserved as “tests” to make sure the model works on unseen inputs. Popular practices like k-fold cross-validation, where the training data is split randomly into “folds” and one fold is left for testing each time, can be employed to increase the reliability of the model (Steyerberg et al. 776). The second type is external validation: the model should be tested on datasets outside the development process (Riley et al. 1). In this way, researchers will be able to simulate more realistic situations and gain a better insight into how consistently the model performs “out in the wild”. Of course, it may be difficult to find external datasets that fit perfectly with the model, and not all models can be generalised, as discussed towards the end of Section 2.1. van de Sande et al. alternatively recommended that, in these circumstances, “the concept based on the specific variables and outcomes” should be validated instead (4). Either way, during external validation, any discrepancies with the expected result must be analysed, and the model should be retrained if required.

The fourth step, after the model has reached satisfactory accuracy on static datasets, is to conduct clinical trials to further monitor the model based on dynamic, genuine patient data. Developers and clinical physicians must work together to design large-scale, randomised, controlled tests (van de Sande et al. 5). This is to observe both the output of the AI model, compared to a doctor’s opinion, and patients’ responses to this process of AI-assisted diagnosis. It is the prime time for developers to tweak and alter parts of the system, and make it more

useful to physicians or friendly to patients (see Section 4.1 for a discussion of the importance of patient reactions to healthcare AI). As the system reaches a stage of wider implementation, the producer should continue a long-term collaboration with the healthcare institution to account for any incidents occurring after the general availability roll-out. As noted by van de Sande et al., paradigms may shift in the field of healthcare quickly, requiring constant updates to the algorithm (5). The model must be under active development to encompass these rapid changes, and healthcare professionals must continuously evaluate its trustworthiness to support them in clinical decision-making and ensure sustained responsible use.

On a universal level, cutting-edge technologies as complex to explain as AI require an atmosphere of open science with a culture of transparent sharing and participant-centred development (Norori et al. 5–7). Richardson warned that healthcare AI developers must “engage the public in dialogue” to keep the audience of these AI systems informed of the potential benefits and harms (4). In terms of equity in resource distribution, Brady and Neri pointed out that while financial incentives are vital to the continued innovation in healthcare AI, it should be the ultimate objective to ensure that the benefits can be enjoyed by all patients in healthcare systems across countries, especially those with a high demand for AI, to compensate for a shortage in healthcare professionals (5).

3 Transparency, accountability, and liability

Within and outside the field of medicine, the maintenance of transparency and the establishment of “Explainable Artificial Intelligence” (XAI), especially when it comes to

consumer-facing AI, have received more awareness with the development of more complex AI systems (Adadi and Berrada 52138; Biran and Cotton 1; Shaban-Nejad et al. 2). The ultimate goal for XAI is to create explainable products that “enable end users to understand, appropriately trust, and effectively manage the emerging generation of AI systems”, so that patients and healthcare professionals can understand and trust AI-produced output (Amedior 7; Gunning and Aha 45).

Although XAI is an appropriate guiding objective, the statement above seems to be too vague and prone to misleading interpretation in a real-life context. How is it possible to measure and quantify end users’ comprehension levels for an AI system? What measures are required to establish trust between the vendors, users, and beneficiaries? Who is responsible for managing these systems and their decisions? Disagreements over these key questions could lead to a potentially disastrous deviation in our moral compass.

3.1 The transparency fallacy

The belief that the AI industry can be completely “transparent” is summarised concisely by Edwards and Veale under the umbrella term: the “transparency fallacy” (65). It encompasses four aspects: privacy, security, intellectual property, and complexity.

To begin with, a loose definition of “transparency” could lead to severe privacy concerns. For instance, a research model will naturally be more “transparent” than a commercial product, in that its functioning is accessible to anyone who can read the associated publication, not just the internal developers at a particular company. In addition, it is common for researchers to

release the source code, and, at times, the dataset used to test the model. This contributes to the “reproducibility” and increases the credibility of the research (Bi et al. 149; Carter et al. 1; Maier-Hein et al. 2). On the other hand, production-grade or commercial AI systems are usually much more complex and consider more feature labels when generating output. For healthcare-related AI, the dataset used to train the model could potentially include sensitive patient data, such as their electronic medical records (EMR), which, if leaked, could lead to “a breach of confidentiality” (Hovorushchenko et al. 7). This needs to be examined on a case-by-case basis to comply with privacy and personal data regulations.

Closely related to privacy concerns is the issue of security. Releasing the entire source code implies the danger of suffering the same problems as open-source software, where “hackers could place back doors [...] that could permit unauthorized entry to systems” (Lawton 21). An especially concerning consequence is known as “zero-day vulnerabilities”, or vulnerabilities that could be exploited before the producer of the software becomes aware and produces a patch (Libicki et al. 16). Once the healthcare industry becomes dependent on AI products, especially for clinical practices, revealing the source code to the public could lead to a malicious actor taking advantage of these vulnerabilities to gain illegitimate access to patient data, interfere with the model output, or even paralyse the entire healthcare system.

The third aspect of the transparency fallacy is the protection of intellectual property and trade secrets. This strategy provides the company with a competitive advantage and incentivises investments in the research and development of innovative technologies (Kitchin 20; Schönberger 195). It is especially important in healthcare, due to the ever-changing nature

of the field, with frequent medical breakthroughs that require the producers to respond to the market promptly. Therefore, a regulation that violates AI companies' rights to protect their copyrighted work will ultimately demotivate them from keeping their models up to date, decreasing efficiency and increasing the danger of misdiagnosis.

The last aspect to be aware of is the well-known trade-off between explainability and complexity, as “a system that is explainable is typically not very efficient” (Dunlap et al. 117). As larger models tend to be more difficult to explain, requests for justifiable output may rule out more performant and intricate algorithms that could potentially be adopted instead. As a result, “explainable” AI algorithms may take more time to suggest a decision and yield less accurate judgements, decreasing their usability.

3.2 Addressing the transparency fallacy

There is no clear-cut solution to the transparency fallacy. Ultimately, different AI products and users have distinctive use cases that cannot be simplified to a universal elucidation of what “transparency” entails. Nonetheless, some countermeasures may help partially mitigate the risk and reduce the potential impact while making as much information accessible as possible.

One of the key ideas is to limit the scope of access. When discussing “transparency”, one may falsely assume that information will be released to anyone in the public; however, a company does not need to share sensitive details openly for everyone to view. Rather, it may selectively filter information for trusted intermediary agents responsible for relaying the information to other stakeholders. This intermediary could be, for instance, a frontline

healthcare institution that uses an AI model to assist judgement in clinical diagnosis. In this case, the practitioners must be educated on the medically relevant details of how the model reaches its conclusions to make the results professionally useful; however, they will not need to gain access to the source code or the training dataset, nor will they describe the technicalities of the model to the patients. Another example could be a government legal agency or an independent review board with an obligation to investigate medical AI incidents. In this case, they may have the right to request the source code and, if they have the legal right to view relevant sensitive records, the training data. Similarly, the public version of the investigation report should not disclose specific details.

Of course, this would raise further concerns about who should decide on these intermediaries, and where the source of their power lies. When the process involves a governmental body, for instance, it opens possibilities for political prosecution or censorship. A government could abuse this power to disrupt the operations of foreign AI providers as a diplomatic bargaining chip or to suppress information about a certain illness in AI systems for the sake of glorifying political achievements. Furthermore, according to Ramsauer et al., granting certain parties the special privilege to bypass certain privacy or safety protection measures in software development indicates that “trusted individuals can easily infiltrate the project, and secretly introduce malicious artefacts”; obscuring the patching process of security vulnerabilities may make them more conspicuous for attackers to uncover (147, 155).

Another approach to safeguard the privacy and security of these AI products could be requiring vendors to provide a record similar to a software bill of materials (SBOM), which is “a

list of all included software components” that provides “a transparency mechanism for securing software product supply chains” (Carmody et al. 1). A case in point is when the President of the United States, after the 2021 Apache Log4J incident, signed an Executive Order to make SBOMs mandatory for software used by governmental agencies (Savage 14; Biden, Executive Order 14028). In a healthcare AI context, providing a list of the dependencies of the software, along with their privacy and security policies, enables healthcare institutions to make a more informed choice on the reliability of these systems.

Recent technological developments, especially GPT models, see a trend of “self-justifying” models. Instead of relying on third parties to help explain the model’s output and results, many have started to look at ways to make AI describe how it reached its conclusions. A recent example is Microsoft’s Bing AI, which adds credibility to its generated answers by incorporating the Bing search engine and citing sources from the Internet (Mehdi). Similarly, Assistant by scite is an academic GPT fine-tuned on a set of labelled academic publications that can aid researchers in finding related works, answering questions, and reviewing diverse opinions (Nicholson et al. 887–88). They both show the search queries used to obtain those results, which helpfully supports how it eventually formed its output. These features reduce the possibility of “hallucination”, when the model makes up citations that do not exist, identified by multiple researchers as one of the major problems concerning AI trustworthiness in research, healthcare, and general applications (Alkaissi and McFarlane 3; Athaluri et al. 1; Gilson et al.; Ji et al. 248:2; Lee 1; P. Lee et al. 1233). Most notably, these features provide a way for users to verify the model’s responses. However, it is still worth mentioning that even with citations and

thought outlines, hallucinations may still occur, due to the dependency of the models on the prompt. It is well-known that humans exhibit response biases when responding to positively- or negatively-worded surveys (Chyung et al. 17). In a similar manner, large language models can misinterpret or inaccurately paraphrase the sources to “fit” the question, which could occur if the prompt contains a subtle, misleading assumption that the model adopts in its answer. By prompting the same model with different variations of the same prompt, the bias level in the output can significantly vary (Akyürek et al. 559). Therefore, the prompt used in production needs to be carefully engineered and tested to minimise misguidance.

OpenAI, the company behind the most popular GPT models, has attempted to explain GPT-2 with GPT-4 under the heading of “Automated interpretability” (Bills et al.; OpenAI). This advancement is ground-breaking. If AI models succeed in directly explaining themselves, they will gain the ability to self-iterate and contribute to the maintenance of XAI. A more accessible and arguably more successful attempt is the recent GitHub Copilot X Technical Preview, another GPT model that can explain the purpose of any block of code (Dohmke). If it can explain AI models from the code level, then it would be entirely possible for this ability to be transferred to a more abstract level.

3.3 Accountability and liability

Across academia and legislative bodies, there are different voices about AI responsibility. On the one hand, the European Commission argued that AI models are not eligible to assume moral responsibility because machines and algorithms can never have “autonomy”; it is a term that implies human agency and dignity and provides ethical grounding (9–10). For this reason,

an arrangement, commonly referred to as the “human-in-the-loop”, is often adopted by proponents of the AI-assisted decision-making process (Mosqueira-Rey et al. 3005; Schönberger 193). To put it simply, a human must be involved and make the “final call”, for which they will bear responsibility. An inexact yet useful analogy: AI at its current stage is comparable to a child who, after committing a wrongful action, may not be held morally responsible due to the lack of cognitive and moral development necessary to understand the consequences of the action (Arthur 269). For this reason, the responsibility for any AI-generated suggestions must fall on a “scapegoat” individual or institution. This solution is plausible and reassuring because it does not require any changes to existing systems of liability. Legal and ethical codes may still be applied ordinarily without modification.

On the other hand, there are also concerns raised by this structure. Shrestha et al., for instance, specifically mentioned how requiring human intervention in the decision-making process could lead to a reduction in replicability and speed (74). Schönberger also proposed the benefits of using fully-automated AI as a means to reduce the stress on the limited number of healthcare professionals in less developed countries (194). The trade-off between trustworthiness and efficiency is a problem that needs to be agreed upon depending on the situation. Removing humans from an automation workflow involving AI should not be a morally reproachable act, especially considering this approach is likely to result in the adoption of AI systems in under-staffed regions and enable more equitable access to AI for all (see also Section 2.2); nevertheless, there is still a duty to explain the situation to patients, as well as to

compensate for any unexpected consequences, and it must be assumed by some party involved.

As exhibited above, one critical question remains regardless of the framework: who should undertake the liability? The human-in-the-loop approach rules out AI itself as a moral agent, but there are two other major human participants in the decision process: AI software vendors and healthcare professionals. Indeed, the liable party for an incident often depends on its nature, severity, and magnitude. In general, though, both parties should be somewhat responsible. AI producers have a responsibility to develop models with safe and reliable quality and suitable to healthcare professionals' actual needs (Wang et al. 1). Healthcare professionals have more theoretical experience, but they also have the responsibility to learn the proper operations of the system as well as its limitations (Castagno and Khalifa 4; Jha et al. 935). This reduces the possibility of misdiagnosis due to misuse or misunderstanding of the system. It is also worth noting that accountability in healthcare can be attributed to more than 11 parties, such as payers, investors, and professional associations (Emanuel and Emanuel 230). Based on these considerations, the WHO guidance published by Reis et al. suggests the adoption of "collective responsibility", considering "all the agents involved in the development and deployment" without considering the intention or the participation of each party. In this way, all actors will try to avoid causing harm as much as possible (28). However, asserting whether this framework is just requires more in-depth discussion and review of potential scenarios, especially in cases where one party inflicts considerably more harm than the others.

An alternative long-term approach is to develop AI systems with ethical values and morality in mind so that they would eventually evolve into “entities” capable of making ethical decisions and being morally judged by other humans or machines. This is known as “Value Sensitive Design” (VSD), a “theoretically grounded approach to the design of technology that accounts for human values in a principled and comprehensive manner throughout the design process” (Friedman et al. 56). Proponents of “machine ethics” believe that similar to how children grow up, AI will align with human values and moral standards in the long run, and demonstrate morally responsible behaviour as it becomes more intelligent (Awad et al. 13; Smith and Vickers 492). Some scholars argue that there is no necessary connection between the high intelligence of a system and the comprehension of morality (Armstrong 82); however, it does not contradict the possibility of developing highly-intelligent systems that can simultaneously acknowledge morality. There are existing experiments on using AI to make ethical judgements, such as the research prototype Delphi (Jiang et al.). One may argue that Delphi does not possess morality of its own, but has rather merely spotted patterns from the data the researchers chose to feed it; however, many publications support the claim that humans, too, establish moral values by learning from society and others (Lindemann 44; Nelson; Xiong 1119). Delphi serves as an excellent starting point for further investigation into the possibility of assigning liability directly to AI agents. This will be a more robust ethical solution that eliminates the necessity to discuss the involvement of humans, albeit a revolutionary paradigm shift in the perception of the scope of ethical agents would likely precede the acceptance of this notion.

4 *Autonomy, consent, and patient-centred care*

In their recent publication, Dai and Tayur proposed the “4Ps” of AI adoption in healthcare: physician buy-in, patient acceptance, provider investment and payer support (4444). Notably, patient acceptance forms one of the fundamental pillars. Patient responses are undoubtedly decisive in determining the success of AI software (Lin et al. 1628). Similarly, Asan et al. pointed out the importance of the trust between patients, physicians and AI systems, since patients are ultimately the ones to directly experience the impact (5). Thus, clinical healthcare AI must be designed to suit the needs of the patients and ensure they receive the best quality of service.

4.1 *The role of patients and informed consent*

Two major factors shape patient reactions towards AI tools: their understanding of risk mitigation, and their engagement with the product. In terms of risk mitigation, they must be informed of the measures that healthcare professionals are taking to ensure data privacy, security, safety, patient autonomy, etc. (Richardson et al. 2). The first three aspects are extensively examined in Section 3. Concerning patient autonomy, Richardson et al. reported that patients prefer to have the option to opt out of AI-assisted healthcare workflows and to voice their opinions if they find AI recommendations to be unsuitable (3). Esmailzadeh agreed that, despite lacking professional knowledge, patients must have the right to highlight any concerns they may have regarding AI tools used by clinical physicians; AI systems should respect patients’ autonomy and must not be coercive (3, 16). It is the healthcare provider’s role to inform the patient truthfully about any AI products that would assist with the diagnosis before the process begins, and no AI-based action should be carried out without the patient’s

explicit, informed consent. Especially in a human-in-the-loop framework, after a verdict is given by the AI and reviewed by the practitioner in charge, the patient should be briefed as clearly as possible on the rationale behind the diagnosis, regardless of the complexity of the AI system and the ability for even healthcare professionals to fully conceptualise its decision process (Astromskè et al. 516; Kawamleh). They should then be offered the opportunity to raise any questions, identical to a fully human consultation process.

One important question, related to Section 3.2, is the extent to which technical details are mandatory to avoid compromising patients' autonomy and their ability to give informed consent. Schönberger argued that "the right of individuals to information disclosure is not an end in itself", but rather associated with significant "material risks" for the patients (188). He also pointed out that the introduction of AI would not change the extent to which details should be shared with patients, as AI is simply a "more advanced [technique] for analysing data" (188). Similarly, the UK Supreme Court specified that the "advisory role" for doctors "will only be performed effectively if the information provided is comprehensible"; doctors cannot fulfil their duty by "bombarding the patient with technical information which [they] cannot reasonably be expected to grasp" (*Montgomery* par. 90). Considering these views, providing technical details beyond the patients' professional knowledge is not helpful towards and not sufficient for informed consent.

Patient engagement is mostly applicable to patient-facing tools and comprises two criteria: user-initiated engagement and system-initiated engagement. In a user-initiated scenario, a patient proactively contacts a healthcare institution. In this case, as the desired effect is

efficiency and reduced workflow for human healthcare workers, the foremost goal is to ensure the user sees value in interacting with the AI product, a chatbot for example, and using it to its fullest. Designing it in a way that feels discouraging to the users would lead to their requesting responses from human physicians, leaving the AI product unused and wasted (Esmailzadeh 2). In a system-initiated scenario, a patient may be participating in a long-term health plan that requires the healthcare institute to reach out to them for reminders. However, following up with every patient takes a significant amount of manpower, while automated routine notifications may feel too unspecific to be motivating or accurate to a patient's distinct conditions. This is an area where AI could assist in driving "nuanced interventions" and tailoring personalised recommendations for each patient in their course of treatment, increasing the probability of patient adherence (Davenport and Kalakota 96).

4.2 Reducing misdiagnosis

Regardless of knowledge and skills, all clinical physicians are prone to misdiagnosis caused by cognitive biases such as status quo bias, anchoring bias, availability bias, present bias and social norms, resulting in suboptimal treatment, oversight of preventative care and harmful peer comparison (Bate et al. 618; C. S. Lee et al. 612; Mishra et al. 2–3). Most doctors would make a diagnosis "within the first 18 seconds of seeing a patient", reflecting their anchoring and correspondence biases (Groopman); there are also cases of delayed diagnosis due to the influence of cognitive biases in the treating clinician (Brown et al. 1–3).

While AI certainly cannot eliminate all biases, as discussed in Section 2, it has been proven to mitigate various risks when the physician adheres to the second opinion provided by the AI

(Brown et al. 5; Char et al. 981; K. Lee et al. 2181; Markowitz et al. 410; Murphy et al. 9). Notably, the United Nations reported a decrease in diagnostic error rate from 3.5% to 0.5% with AI assistance (Begovic et al.). Since the process of clinical decision-making requires much experience with different cases, AI could make a more knowledgeable judgement thanks to the sheer magnitude of data it has access to (Bate et al. 614; Sackett et al. 71). Its insensitivity to the specific order of patients also avoids availability/recency bias, since the diagnosis of more recent patients does not have an immediate effect on that of the next one (Dilsizian and Siegel 1–2; AI Now 2; Paul et al. 2; Safavi). Anchoring bias, involving overreliance on initial information provided by the patient, can be prevented by designing AI systems in such a way that all information can be input at once (Dilsizian and Siegel 1–2; AI Now 2). Dilsizian and Siegel also highlighted that AI can be less susceptible to framing bias, the satisfaction of search and premature closure (1–2); Brown et al. brought up fatigue as another problem AI avoids (5). In short, while there may be obstacles caused by AI in the healthcare workflow, it is also crucial to recognise a lower chance of human error in AI-assisted diagnosis.

5 Conclusion and future work

This work discussed the various ethical consequences of implementing AI in healthcare from three main angles: fairness, transparency, and autonomy. Some potential solutions to the problems have also been offered, including approaches to mitigate biases (Section 2.2), maximise transparency (Section 3.2), assign responsibility (Section 3.3) and preserve patient autonomy (Section 4.1).

While the issues are pressing and morally significant, the purpose of this work is not to dissuade the introduction of AI in healthcare. On the complete contrary, identifying these issues should help the agencies and institutions involved build a systematic evaluation of the proposal. Despite numerous challenges, AI has potential use in optimising logistics, automating medical documentation, analysing patient experience, assisting in gene editing, suggesting imaging options for radiologists, making management decisions and interacting with patients through the hardware (Fenech et al. 12–13). Therefore, instead of killing off the opportunity, these obstacles should provoke more debate in the field to further the quality of AI healthcare services.

Future work may focus on the partially explained or answered questions mentioned in this work, such as the fairness of the “collective responsibility” model proposed by the WHO (see Section 2.2) and the assessment for a morally responsible AI agent (see Section 3.3). Additionally, since the cost-benefit analysis provided in this work is primarily utilitarian, it would be valuable to examine the matter with different ethical frameworks to cover additional repercussions like individual rights.

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